

Transverse Vibration of Non-Homogeneous Rectangular Plates of Variable Thickness Using GDQ

Authors : R. Saini, R. Lal

Abstract : The effect of non-homogeneity on the free transverse vibration of thin rectangular plates of bilinearly varying thickness has been analyzed using generalized differential quadrature (GDQ) method. The non-homogeneity of the plate material is assumed to arise due to linear variations in Young's modulus and density of the plate material with the in-plane coordinates x and y . Numerical results have been computed for fully clamped and fully simply supported boundary conditions. The solution procedure by means of GDQ method has been implemented in a MATLAB code. The effect of various plate parameters has been investigated for the first three modes of vibration. A comparison of results with those available in literature has been presented.

Keywords : rectangular, non-homogeneous, bilinear thickness, generalized differential quadrature (GDQ)

Conference Title : ICCSAM 2014 : International Conference on Computer Science and Applied Mathematics

Conference Location : Singapore, SG

Conference Dates : September 11-12, 2014